

Abstract

The 'Epley Area': A New Cranial Acupuncture Site for Vertigo and Dizziness.

Paula Sousa^{1,2*}, Jorge Rodrigues^{1,2}, Madalena Deus², Mariana Pedrosa², Raquel Parreira², Fabrício Pereira³, Jorge Machado^{1,2}, and António Moreira⁴.

¹ ICBAS – School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, Portugal;

² CBSin - Centre of Biosciences in Integrative Health, Porto, Portugal;

³ MIPA, Université de Nîmes, Nîmes, France;

⁴ CIDESD - Research Centre in Sports, Health and Human Development, Vila Real, Portugal.

* Correspondence: pasousa32@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: It is estimated that 20% to 30% of adults experience dizziness or vertigo at some point in their lives. Primary causes include dysfunctions of the peripheral vestibular system and the central nervous system, such as cerebrovascular disorders, Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo, hyperventilation syndrome, and inner ear diseases (e.g., Ménière's disease and vestibular neuritis). Other contributing factors include cardiovascular disease, adverse drug reactions, age-related vestibular decline, and whiplash syndrome. In clinical practice, these syndromes are frequently observed and can be highly disabling, significantly impairing a patient's quality of life and functional independence.

Objective: Evaluate the clinical efficacy of a novel cranial acupuncture intervention in three adult patients presenting with persistent vertigo or dizziness.

Methods: A pioneer cranial acupuncture technique was applied to a newly proposed anatomical site, designated as the 'Epley Area'. Treatment involved bilateral needling, with each session lasting 60 minutes. Symptom severity was monitored using a VAS, administered immediately before and after each clinical session to track real-time progress.

Results: Following a course of four acupuncture sessions, all three patients reported complete resolution of their vertigo and dizziness. Notably, one patient with comorbid tinnitus reported a significant reduction in its intensity. These preliminary findings suggest that the 'Epley Area' may be a highly effective site for neuromodulatory intervention. Robust randomised controlled trials are required to validate these results and establish standardised protocols.

Citation: Sousa P., Rodrigues J., Deus M., Pedrosa M., Parreira R., Pereira F., Machado J., Moreira A. The 'Epley Area': A New Cranial Acupuncture Site for Vertigo and Dizziness. *Journal of Complementary Therapies in Health*. 2026;4(2) 10.5281/zenodo.19887892

Publisher's Note: IPTC stays neutral concerning jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2026 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Keywords: Dizziness; Vertigo; Acupuncture; Scalp Acupuncture; Epley Area; Vestibular Rehabilitation.

Acknowledgements: This work was presented at the 1st Scientific Seminars of Complementary Therapies in Health, on 26 September 2025.